
ANALYSIS OF THE SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF SYNONYMS IN ENGLISH.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7856188>

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Abstract.

In the modern world, the synonyms of different languages are given serious attention and they are analyzed, because knowledge of the synonymous wealth of the language is considered one of the important conditions of human speech culture, and scientists have conducted scientific works on this topic. The reserve of synonyms of the studied language allows to master new skills qualitatively and to overcome the language barrier in communication.

Keywords.

English language, analyse, thoughts, Uzbek language, synonyms, analysis, dictionaries, pronunciation, similar aspects.

Introduction.

Synonyms are different words with the same or similar meaning, and scholars have given similar definitions to them in different books. They occur in every part of speech, including nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, and prepositions.[1] In the modern world, it is necessary to pay serious attention to synonymy, because knowledge of the synonymous wealth of the language is an important condition of human speech culture. In addition, the reserve of synonyms of the studied language allows to master new skills qualitatively and overcome the language barrier in communication. The relevance of this work lies in its practical value. The essence of synonymy and the synonymous relationship between words have long attracted the attention of linguists.[6] Synonymy is based on the ability of the language system to have more than one sign for one sign, from the Greek word synonymy - "homonymy", and helps to express in language various features of the objective world using minimal linguistic means. The emergence of borrowed words is not the only reason for the appearance of synonyms in the language, although as a result of the peculiarities of the historical development of the English language, it

played a very important role in the development of borrowed words. 10] However, synonyms can also appear as a result of the appearance of new meanings of words in the language, affixation, conversion, word formation, and the appearance of stable word combinations.[5]

The relevance of the topic is that despite the fact that many scholars have studied synonyms in English and Uzbek, its relevance has not yet disappeared. We can see the results of different scientists comparing the analysis, similarities and translations of synonyms, and this is still going on. If we analyze the similar and different aspects of synonyms, for example: the words beautiful, beautiful, husnli, husndor, khushroy, kokhli, zebo, suluv, sahibjamol. Among the synonyms, the word "beautiful" is a synonym with such signs.[10] The rest of the words are different from each other with their own characteristics of the sign, for example, the word beautiful expresses the sign with a strong high level, the words barno, zebo have a more bookish style, and the word leech is used relatively rarely. As an analysis of the literature, it is possible to observe the scientific works of several scientists. Comparison of synonyms in English and Uzbek languages has become a research object of many linguists. Many literatures were used in writing this research paper. In particular, Mirzaakbarov S. in 2021 from the journal "The importance of teaching synonyms in English and Uzbek", In addition, W.E. Collinson, "Comparative Synonymics: Some Principles and Illustrations", Transactions of the Philological Society and many similar books were used.[10]

As part of the experiment, the works of several scientists were analyzed, examples of this scientific work were taken and analyzed: the original name of Roget's thesaurus perfectly captures the importance of thesauruses and the synonyms they provide - "A Thesaurus of Words and Phrases in the English Language, Representing Ideas" classified and arranged so as to facilitate and aid literary composition". When writing, you may struggle to find the best way to express yourself. This is because some words just don't convey the depth of feeling, idea or emotion you want to express.

A thesaurus and its seemingly endless synonyms will help with this[2]. Synonyms can help you avoid empty words like "really" and "very" and make your writing stronger[9]. For example, let's say you're a realtor trying to close on a house. Instead of saying that the lake looks "very nice", you can say:

The house has a stunning view of the lake.

The house has a picturesque view of the lake.

The house has a glorious view of the lake.

The house has an exquisite view of the lake[9].

Analysis and results. The main goal of organizing a pilot test of the comparative analysis of synonyms in English and Uzbek languages is to develop training material aimed at enriching the synonomic reserve of language learners using the synonymy method in the course of the English language lesson.[7] This training material helps English language learners to use synonyms correctly and increase their vocabulary in the learning process. Based on this dissertation, experimental and numerical studies and evaluation of its results were evaluated based on a number of official and regulatory documents.

Using the method of synonymy to organize an experimental test of the comparative analysis of synonyms in English and Uzbek, the development of training material aimed at enriching the synonomic reserve of language learners was carried out in several stages, and the following three stages included: first stage - analysis and classification of synonyms in English and Uzbek languages, study of their origin. Analysis of English and Uzbek dictionaries.[9] Studying and analyzing the researches of foreign and Uzbek linguists. Creating a set of exercises by developing a text in English and using the synonymy method in this text, preparing for the test and developing evaluation criteria; the second stage-conducting pilot-testing works at the HEI base; the third stage consists of analyzing the obtained results, bringing them into one system and formalizing them. [8]

There are two main uses of synonyms, which we will detail below: Synonyms can improve word choice or choose the best word for what you want to communicate. Synonyms are needed to avoid overusing the same word. [4]

Summary. The conclusion of this research work, i.e., the development of vocabulary during the comparative analysis of synonyms in English and Uzbek languages, is that: English and Uzbek synonyms are currently considered by many scholars to be Uzbek. is being studied. But this does not mean that the relevance of synonyms is being studied enough. The first chapter of the scientific work is a general interpretation of synonyms, in which the history of the origin of synonyms and the classification of similar and different aspects of their types were studied. The scientific works of several foreign scientists and the scientific works of Uzbek linguists were analyzed. Among them, foreign scientists: V. A. Grechko. A. V. Lagutina, E. N. Tolikina, V. P. Danilenko, A. T. Bevzenko, Y. D. Apresyan, S. A. Belyaeva, T. I. Panko and Uzbek linguists: U. Tursunov, N. Rajabov, S. Isamammedova, A. Doniyorov, S. Usmanov, A. Khojiyev , I. Kochkortoyev, R. Yunusov, M. Askarova's works were studied and analyzed. The second chapter of

the scientific work is the classification of synonyms in English and Uzbek languages. In this, the origin and analysis of synonym dictionaries in English and Uzbek languages, the classification of similar and different aspects of synonyms in English and Uzbek languages were highlighted with the help of examples.

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